

Occurrence and Clinical Predictors of Bleeding Complications in Non-Obese Patients Undergoing Primary Percutaneous Coronary Intervention

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Bleeding is a major complication associated with increased mortality in “ST elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI)” patients. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the frequency and predictors of post-procedural bleeding complications among non-obese patients undergoing primary “percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI)”.

Methods: This descriptive cross-sectional study included a consecutive series of non-obese patients diagnosed with STEMI who underwent primary PCI. The patients were continuously observed for a maximum of 72 hours during their hospital stay, and any bleeding complications (minor/major) were recorded. Major bleeding was defined as a decrease in hemoglobin $\geq 5\text{g/dL}$ and a decrease in hematocrit $\geq 15\%$ from the baseline at 72 hours. Minor bleeding was defined as a decrease in hemoglobin $\geq 3\text{g/dL}$ but a hematocrit $< 15\%$ from the baseline at 72 hours.

Results: This study evaluated 244 non-obese patients, with a mean age of 46.4 ± 13.3 years, male patients were 60.7% (148) of the sample, and the mean body mass index (BMI) was $21.9 \pm 3.1\text{ kg/m}^2$, with 16.4% (40) having a BMI below 18.5 kg/m^2 . Trans-radial access was the chosen access for 95.9% (234) of the procedures. Bleeding occurred in 6.6% (16) of patients, with 2.05% (5) categorized as major and 4.51% (11) as minor bleeding events. The trans-femoral access was found to be an independent predictor of bleeding, with an adjusted odds ratio of 12.47 [2.88-54.01; $p=0.001$].

Conclusion: Based on the research findings, bleeding is not an uncommon complication, especially after primary PCI through trans-femoral access.

Keywords: STEMI, primary PCI, non-obese, complications, bleeding, trans-femoral access

INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is the primary cause of illness and death on a global scale. The burden of CVD in “low- and middle-income countries (LMICs)” is increasing at an alarming rate, as compared to the high-income communities. This presents a significant global problem, considering that LMICs make up approximately 80% of the global population [1]. The most common and life-threatening manifestation of CVD is “ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction (STEMI)” [2]. Although outcomes for STEMI patients have improved significantly due to

widespread use of primary “percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI)”, evidence-based pharmacological regimens, and advancements in stenting and deployment techniques [2,3], it remains a leading cause of premature deaths and “disability-adjusted life years (DALYs)” worldwide, particularly in LMICs [1]. The impact extends beyond health, as STEMI predominantly affects working-age individuals in LMICs, leading to direct and indirect financial implications [4]. Unfortunately, not all patients with acute STEMI have favorable outcomes, as a substantial number of them experience adverse events within 30 days following the initial procedure, with rates ranging from 2.5% to 10% [5-7]. These events can vary in severity and include cardiogenic shock, heart failure, arrhythmias, ventricular remodeling, recurrent myocardial infarction, thromboembolic events, valvular dysfunction, and sudden cardiac death [8]. The occurrence and severity of these adverse events depend on factors such as the extent and location of the myocardial infarction, pre-existing health conditions, and timely access to medical intervention [9,10].

Bleeding, whether related to the access site or non-access site, is a significant adverse event in patients with “acute coronary syndromes (ACS)” who undergo cardiac catheterization and PCI [12]. Bleeding is among the major complications of percutaneous intervention found associated with an increased risk of mortality and morbidity in STEMI patients. There are certain clinical and demographic factors found to be associated with an increased risk of bleeding in STEMI include female gender, advanced age, history of bleeding, a lower body mass index, and cardiogenic shock [12]. Furthermore, it has been observed that patients of Asian origin have a higher risk of bleeding [12]. Our current understanding of bleeding in ACS patients with STEMI primarily relies on information from published scientific papers, which mostly report on randomized clinical trials that tend to include lower-risk patients compared to those treated in real-life settings [13].

There are three main bleeding risk scores available: the CRUSADE risk score [14], the ACTION Registry-GWTG risk score [15], and the ACUTY-HORIZONS bleeding risk score [16]. However, none of these scores were specifically developed for STEMI patients [17]. It has also been reported that Asian patients have higher rates of bleeding complications after PCI despite of having fewer traditional coronary risk factors compared to their Western counterparts, likely due to their low body mass index [12,18]. Nevertheless, limited data exist on bleeding complications in the Asian population, and previous large-scale registry studies have relatively low representation of Asian subgroups [18]. Given the differences in risk profiles between Pakistani patients and those in Western populations, it is necessary to independently assess the incidence and predictors of bleeding complications after PCI in our population. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the frequency and predictors of post-procedural bleeding complications among non-obese patients undergoing primary PCI.

METHODOLOGY

This study was conducted at the “National Institute of Cardiovascular Diseases (NICVD)”, the largest cardiac care center in Pakistan. The research proposal was approved by the research and evaluation unit (REU) of the “College of Physicians and Surgeons of Pakistan (CPSP)” as part of the fellowship program in adult cardiology. The study duration was six months, from March 6th, 2019, to September 6th, 2019. Verbal informed consent was obtained from all the participating patients in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki.

Patients for this descriptive cross-sectional study were selected using a non-probability consecutive sampling technique. The specific inclusion criteria were as follows: patients of either gender, aged between 20 to 70 years, non-obese, diagnosed with STEMI, and underwent PCI. Patients who refused to give consent for participation,

those with a history of cardiac surgery or intervention, or patients who died during the procedure (on-table) were excluded.

As part of the routine STEMI management protocol, a 12-lead electrocardiogram (ECG) was obtained, and the diagnosis of STEMI was made based on the presence of typical chest pain history and specific ECG findings according to the fourth universal definition of myocardial infarction [19]. In addition to other clinical assessments, height (cm), weight (kg), and body mass index (BMI, kg/m²) were obtained, and patients with a BMI less than 27.5 kg/m² were considered non-obese.

All primary PCI procedures followed the standard management protocol for STEMI patients. The patients were continuously observed for a maximum of 72 hours during their hospital stay, and any bleeding complications (minor/major) were recorded. Major bleeding was defined as a decrease in hemoglobin \geq 5g/dL and a decrease in hematocrit \geq 15% from the baseline at 72 hours. Minor bleeding was defined as a decrease in hemoglobin \geq 3g/dL but a hematocrit $<$ 15% from the baseline at 72 hours.

Demographic, clinical, and procedure-related characteristics of the patients were recorded, including age (years), gender, smoking status, diabetes mellitus, family history, hypertension, and access for the procedure. All the collected data were recorded on a pre-designed proforma.

The sample size for the study was calculated to be 244, based on a frequency of post-procedure bleeding complications of 4.13% [20], a confidence level of 95%, and a margin of error of 2.5%. The data was entered and analyzed using IBM SPSS, Version 21.0 (Armonk, NY: IBM Corp). Descriptive statistics such as mean \pm SD, median (IQR) were used to express the age (years), height (cm), weight (kg), and BMI (kg/m²) of the patients. Frequency and percentages were calculated for categorical variables such as gender, age group, smoking status, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, family history, access artery, and bleeding complications (minor/major). Confounding factors such as age groups, gender, smoking status, diabetes mellitus, hypertension, family history, and access artery were assessed through stratification. Post-stratification chi-square test or Fisher's exact test was applied. Univariate and multivariable binary logistic regression analyses were performed to determine the predictors of bleeding complications. A two-sided p-value of \leq 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

A total of 244 patients were included with a mean age of 46.4 ± 13.3 years. Male patients were comprised of 60.7% (148) of the study sample. Mean BMI was found to be 21.9 ± 3.1 kg/m² with 16.4% (40) of patients having less than 18.5 kg/m². A majority, 95.9% (234), of the procedures were performed through trans-radial access. Distribution of demographic and clinical data for the study sample are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Distribution of demographic and clinical data for the study sample.

Characteristics	Total
Total (N)	244
Gender	
Female	96 (39.3%)
Male	148 (60.7%)
Age (years)	46.4 ± 13.3
20 to 40 years	82 (33.6%)
41 to 65 years	156 (63.9%)
> 65 years	6 (2.5%)
Height (m)	1.6 ± 0.2

Weight (kg)	52.9 ± 6.6
Body mass index (kg/m²)	21.9 ± 3.1
Less than 18.5 kg/m ²	40 (16.4%)
Between 18.5 to 22.9 kg/m ²	97 (39.8%)
Between 23 to 27.5 kg/m ²	107 (43.9%)
Smoking Status	
Non-smoker	188 (77%)
Smoker	56 (23%)
Diabetes Status	
Non-diabetic	157 (64.3%)
Diabetic	87 (35.7%)
Hypertension Status	
Non-hypertensive	169 (69.3%)
Hypertensive	75 (30.7%)
Access Artery	
Femoral	10 (4.1%)
Radial	234 (95.9%)
Bleeding Event	
No	228 (93.4%)
Yes	16 (6.6%)

Bleeding occurred in 6.6% (16) of patients with five (2.05%) categorized as major and 11 (4.51%) as minor bleeding events. The occurrence of bleeding event was higher with trans-femoral access for procedure compared to trans-radial access with frequency of 40% (4/10) vs. 5.1% (12/234); p<0.001. Frequency of bleeding stratified by various demographic and clinical characteristics are presented in **Table 2**.

Table 2: Frequency of bleeding stratified by various demographic and clinical characteristics

Characteristics	Base (N)	Bleeding Event		P-value
		No	Yes	
Total (N)		228	0	
Gender				
Female	96	91 (94.8%)	5 (5.2%)	0.493
Male	148	137 (92.6%)	11 (7.4%)	
Age				
20 to 40 years	82	77 (93.9%)	5 (6.1%)	0.774
41 to 65 years	156	145 (92.9%)	11 (7.1%)	
> 65 years	6	6 (100%)	0 (0%)	
Body mass index				
Less than 18.5 kg/m ²	40	39 (97.5%)	1 (2.5%)	0.141
Between 18.5 to 22.9 kg/m ²	97	87 (89.7%)	10 (10.3%)	
Between 23 to 27.5 kg/m ²	107	102 (95.3%)	5 (4.7%)	
Smoking Status				
Non-smoker	188	175 (93.1%)	13 (6.9%)	0.679
Smoker	56	53 (94.6%)	3 (5.4%)	
Diabetes Status				
Non-diabetic	157	148 (94.3%)	9 (5.7%)	0.484
Diabetic	87	80 (92%)	7 (8%)	
Hypertension Status				
Non-hypertensive	169	159 (94.1%)	10 (5.9%)	0.544
Hypertensive	75	69 (92%)	6 (8%)	
Access Artery				
Femoral	10	6 (60%)	4 (40%)	<0.001
Radial	234	222 (94.9%)	12 (5.1%)	

The trans-femoral access for the procedure was found to be an independent predictor of bleeding event with an adjusted odds ratio of 12.47 [2.88-54.01; p=0.001], as presented in [Table 3](#).

Table 3: Univariate and multivariable binary logistic regression analysis for bleeding event

	Univariate		Multivariable	
	OR [95% CI]	P-value	OR [95% CI]	P-value
Male	1.46 [0.49-4.35]	0.495	1.22 [0.38-3.85]	0.739
Age	1.02 [0.98-1.07]	0.262	1.03 [0.98-1.07]	0.224
Body mass index	0.99 [0.84-1.17]	0.905	1.02 [0.85-1.22]	0.828
Smoker	0.76 [0.21-2.77]	0.68	0.75 [0.19-2.92]	0.677
Diabetic	1.44 [0.52-4.01]	0.486	1.53 [0.51-4.60]	0.444
Hypertensive	1.38 [0.48-3.95]	0.546	1.10 [0.34-3.51]	0.877
Femoral access	12.33 [3.07-49.62]	<0.001	12.47 [2.88-54.01]	0.001

DISCUSSION

Bleeding is one of the major complications after percutaneous intervention of STEMI patients and it is a well-established prognostic factors found to be associated with increased risk of mortality morbidity. It has also been reported that Asian patients are at higher risk of bleeding complications after PCI compared to their Western counterparts, nevertheless, limited data exist on bleeding complications after PCI in the Asian population, and previous large-scale registry studies conducted in Western countries have had relatively small Asian subgroups [12,18]. Therefore, the aim of this study was to investigate the frequency and predictors of post-procedural bleeding complications among non-obese patients undergoing primary PCI in our population. We evaluated a series of 244 non-obese patients, the study found that bleeding complications occurred in 6.6% of the patients, with 2.05% classified as major bleeding events and 4.51% as minor bleeding events. Notably, trans-femoral access was identified as an independent predictor of bleeding, with an adjusted odds ratio of 12.47 [2.88-54.01; p=0.001]. These findings suggest that in the context of non-obese patients with STEMI undergoing primary PCI, trans-femoral access carries a significantly higher risk of bleeding complications. Therefore, careful consideration should be given to the choice of access site, with preference given to the trans-radial approach to mitigate the potential for bleeding events.

Studies in past reported frequency of bleeding complications ranging from 1.6% to 10.2% in post PCI patients [20-22]. Numasawa Y *et al.* [22], conducted a multi-center registry based study of 13,075 PCI patients and reported bleeding complication rate of 3.1% with female gender, age, STEMI, non-STEMI, previous heart failure, previous PCI, cardiogenic shock, hemodialysis, use of intra-aortic balloon pump, trans-radial access for the procedure were found to be independent predictors of bleeding on multivariable analysis [22]. A comparatively higher occurrence of bleeding events in Asian population has been reported by Misumida N *et al.* [12], in a study of 46,563 Asian and 1,695,680 white STEMI patients, the incidence of in-hospital major bleeding event was significantly higher among Asian with an incidence rate of 3.6% as compared to 2.2% among white counterparts (p<0.001). Such difference in the risk of bleeding event among Asian population can be partly explained by the differences in demographic and clinical factors, response to the anticoagulation therapies, response to thrombolytic agents, and response to novel antiplatelet agents [12].

As it has been observed in our study that trans-femoral access for the procedure is associated with an increased risk of bleeding, same has been observed by Di Santo P *et al.* [23] in meta-analysis of 14 studies comprises of 11,707 patients with STEMI. It has been reported that trans-radial access, as compared to trans-femoral access, is

associated with a lower risk of bleeding event, access site complications, and 30 days mortality [23]. Lower risk of bleeding associated with trans-radial access has been reported by various other studies [24].

In addition to access site, choice of anticoagulant and antiplatelet therapy are important factors towards risk of bleeding events after PCI. Changes in anticoagulant practice to bivalirudin from glycoprotein IIb/IIIa regimens and heparin resulted in reductions in the incidence of major bleeding and mortality [21]. Adoption of more potent antiplatelet therapies, although have reduced risk of subsequent events after PCI but this has been reported to be counterbalanced by an increased risk of bleeding [25].

The prognostic significance of bleeding cannot be ignored, a meta-analysis of 25 studies by Kwok CS *et al.* [21] reported a risk ratio ranging from 1.6- to 22.7-fold depending on the anatomic source of the bleeding event. The non-access site-related major bleeding event was found to be associated with 4.06-fold [95% CI; 3.21-5.14] risk of mortality as compared to 1.71-fold [95% CI; 1.37-2.13] increased risk of mortality associated with the access site-related major bleeding event [21].

It is important to acknowledge the limitations of our study, including its single-center nature, relatively smaller sample size, and involvement of multiple intervention cardiologists. Further studies with larger sample sizes are warranted to provide additional insights into the risk factors and outcomes related to bleeding complications after primary PCI.

CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, the research findings highlight that bleeding complications are not uncommon following primary PCI, particularly when trans-femoral access is utilized. This suggests that healthcare professionals should be aware of the increased risk of bleeding associated with the trans-femoral approach and take appropriate measures to mitigate and manage this complication. By considering alternative access sites or implementing strategies to minimize bleeding, such as careful patient selection, meticulous procedural technique, and post-procedural monitoring.

REFERENCES

1. [Chandrashekar Y, Alexander T, Mullasari A, Kumbhani DJ, Alam S, Alexanderson E, et al. Resource and infrastructure-appropriate management of ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction in low-and middle-income countries. Circulation. 2020;141\(24\):2004-25.](#)
2. [Krumholz HM, Normand SL, Wang Y. Twenty-year trends in outcomes for older adults with acute myocardial infarction in the United States. JAMA Netw Open. 2019;2\(3\):e191938.](#)
3. [Reed GW, Rossi JE, Cannon CP. Acute myocardial infarction. The Lancet. 2017;389\(10065\):197-210.](#)
4. World Health Organization and World Economic Forum. From Burden to “Best Buys”: Reducing the Economic Impact of NCDs in Low- and Middle-Income Countries. Geneva, Switzerland:World Health Organization;2011.
5. [Taniwaki M, Stefanini GG, Räber L, Brugaletta S, Cequier A, Heg D, et al. Predictors of adverse events among patients undergoing primary percutaneous coronary intervention: insights from a pooled analysis of the COMFORTABLE AMI and EXAMINATION trials. EuroIntervention. 2015;11\(4\):391-8.](#)

6. Kumar R, Shah JA, Solangi BA, Ammar A, Kumar M, Khan N, et al. The Burden of Short-term Major Adverse Cardiac Events and its Determinants after Emergency Percutaneous Coronary Revascularization: A Prospective Follow-up Study. J Saudi Heart Assoc. 2022;34(2):100.
7. McManus DD, Gore J, Yarzebski J, Spencer F, Lessard D, Goldberg RJ. Recent trends in the incidence, treatment, and outcomes of patients with STEMI and NSTEMI. Am J Med. 2011;124(1):40-7.
8. Guo Y, Yin F, Fan C, Wang Z. Gender difference in clinical outcomes of the patients with coronary artery disease after percutaneous coronary intervention: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Medicine. 2018;97(30).
9. Kumar R, Ahmed I, Rai L, Khowaja S, Hashim M, Huma Z, et al. Comparative analysis of four established risk scores for prediction of in-hospital mortality in patients undergoing primary percutaneous coronary intervention. Am J Cardiovasc Dis. 2022;12(6):298-306.
10. Kong S, Chen C, Zheng G, Yao H, Li J, Ye H, et al. A prognostic nomogram for long-term major adverse cardiovascular events in patients with acute coronary syndrome after percutaneous coronary intervention. BMC Cardiovasc Disord. 2021;21(1):253.
11. Porto I, Bolognese L, Dudek D, Goldstein P, Hamm C, Tanguay JF, et al. Impact of access site on bleeding and ischemic events in patients with non-ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction treated with prasugrel: the ACCOAST access substudy. JACC: Cardiovascular Interventions. 2016;9(9):897-907.
12. Misumida N, Ogunbayo GO, Kim SM, Olorunfemi O, Elbadawi A, Charnigo RJ, et al. Higher risk of bleeding in Asians presenting with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction: analysis of the national inpatient sample database. Angiology. 2018;69(6):548-54.
13. Sadjadieh G, Engstrøm T, Høfsten DE, Helqvist S, Køber L, Pedersen F, et al. Bleeding events after ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction in patients randomized to an all-comer clinical trial compared with unselected patients. Am J Cardiol. 2018;122(8):1287-96.
14. Subherwal S, Bach RG, Chen AY, Gage BF, Rao SV, Newby LK, et al. Baseline risk of major bleeding in non-ST-segment-elevation myocardial infarction: The CRUSADE (Can Rapid risk stratification of Unstable angina patients Suppress ADverse outcomes with Early implementation of the ACC/AHA Guidelines) Bleeding Score. Circulation. 2009;119:1873-1882.
15. Mathews R, Peterson ED, Chen AY, Wang TY, Chin CT, Fonarow GC, et al. In-hospital major bleeding during ST-elevation and non-ST-elevation myocardial infarction care: Derivation and validation of a model from the ACTION Registry(R)-GWTG. Am J Cardiol. 2011;107:1136-1143.
16. Mehran R, Pocock SJ, Nikolsky E, Clayton T, Dangas GD, Kirtane AJ, et al. A risk score to predict bleeding in patients with acute coronary syndromes. J Am Coll Cardiol. 2010;55(23):2556-2566.
17. Liu R, Zheng W, Zhao G, Wang X, Zhao X, Zhou S, et al. Predictive validity of CRUSADE, ACTION and ACUTY-HORIZONS bleeding risk scores in Chinese patients with ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction. Circ J. 2018;82(3):791-7.
18. Wang TY, Chen AY, Roe MT, Alexander KP, Newby LK, Smith Jr SC, et al. Comparison of baseline characteristics, treatment patterns, and in-hospital outcomes of Asian versus non-Asian white Americans with non-ST-segment elevation acute coronary syndromes from the CRUSADE quality improvement initiative. Am J Cardiol. 2007;100(3):391-6.

19. Thygesen K, Alpert JS, Jaffe AS, Chaitman BR, Bax JJ, Morrow DA, White HD, Executive Group on behalf of the Joint European Society of Cardiology (ESC)/American College of Cardiology (ACC)/American Heart Association (AHA)/World Heart Federation (WHF) Task Force for the Universal Definition of Myocardial Infarction. Fourth universal definition of myocardial infarction (2018). *Circulation*. 2018;138(20):e618-51.
20. Barthélémy O, Silvain J, Brieger D, Mercadier A, Lancar R, Bellemain-Appaix A, et al. Bleeding complications in primary percutaneous coronary intervention of ST-elevation myocardial infarction in a radial center. *Catheter Cardiovasc Interv*. 2012;79(1):104-12.
21. Kwok CS, Khan MA, Rao SV, Kinnaird T, Sperrin M, Buchan I, et al. Access and non-access site bleeding after percutaneous coronary intervention and risk of subsequent mortality and major adverse cardiovascular events: systematic review and meta-analysis. *Circulation: Cardiovascular Interventions*. 2015;8(4):e001645.
22. Numasawa Y, Kohsaka S, Ueda I, Miyata H, Sawano M, Kawamura A, et al. Incidence and predictors of bleeding complications after percutaneous coronary intervention. *J Cardiol*. 2017;69(1):272-9.
23. Di Santo P, Simard T, Wells GA, Jung RG, Ramirez FD, Boland P, et al. Transradial versus transfemoral access for percutaneous coronary intervention in ST-segment-elevation myocardial infarction: a systematic review and meta-analysis. *Circulation: Cardiovascular Interventions*. 2021;14(3):e009994.
24. Siudak Z, Tokarek T, Dziewierz A, Wysocki T, Wiktorowicz A, Legutko J, et al. Reduced periprocedural mortality and bleeding rates of radial approach in ST-segment elevation myocardial infarction. Propensity score analysis of data from the ORPKI Polish National Registry. *Eurointervention*. 2017;13(7):843-50.
25. Valgimigli M, Costa F, Lokhnygina Y, Clare RM, Wallentin L, Moliterno DJ, et al. Trade-off of myocardial infarction vs. bleeding types on mortality after acute coronary syndrome: lessons from the Thrombin Receptor Antagonist for Clinical Event Reduction in Acute Coronary Syndrome (TRACER) randomized trial. *Eur Heart*. 2017;38(11):804-10.